

per kg soil) in a greenhouse. Each cultivar had six pots with 5 seedlings/pot. The soil was kept flooded until harvest.

Ten seedlings were used for the bleeding sap measurement. At the 7-leaf stage, tillers were removed and the main culm was cut 8 cm above the soil. A cotton of known weight was wrapped around the tip of the cut stem and covered with a small plastic bag. The main culm was then placed in a growth chamber at 15 °C for 6 d. Light intensity was 250 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$ per s and relative humidity, 80%. Bleeding sap from the main culm was measured every 24 h by subtracting the initial weight of the cotton from the final weight and expressed as

weight per unit surface area of the cut end. The other plants were grown under normal temperature up to meiosis, then exposed to 15 °C for 10 d in the growth chamber. The remaining 10 plants were grown under normal conditions until maturity.

Cold-tolerant varieties had higher amounts of bleeding sap than cold-sensitive varieties, and the sap decreased with prolonged exposure to low temperature. Cold-sensitive varieties had higher relative reductions in percent fertility (see table). Spikelet filling percentage and grain yield per plant were positively correlated with the amount of bleeding sap (see figure).

The correlation coefficients between cold tolerance score and amount of bleeding sap under low temperature treatment for 1-6 d (based on values in the table) are 0.51, 0.57, 0.58, 0.29, 0.13, and 0.16, respectively. The r^2 for average amount of bleeding sap versus scale of cold tolerance is 0.81.

Results suggest that the average amount of bleeding sap under low temperature treatment (15 °C) for 6 d could be used as one of the physiological criteria for cold tolerance selection at tillering stage. The selection threshold of bleeding sap should be 2.0 g/cm² per d. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Foliar spraying of K in rice in coastal saline soils

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Integrated rice and prawn culture is popular on Pokkali soils. Flash floods and ingress of sea water through tidal currents are problems. Pokkali soils are medium in available N, high in P, and medium to high in K. Sodium ions in the soil are suspected to hinder the absorption of K through rice roots. A direct source to sink translocation of K should increase K utilization, raise grain

yield, and impart some salinity tolerance to the plant by excluding Na from the shoot. The ability of a cultivar to accumulate K in its shoot correlates well with salt tolerance.

In this study we aimed to provide adequate ionic K concentration in the shoot and to facilitate direct movement of K from the leaf to the grain.

Soil at RRS has pH of 3.5-4.5. Ten rice varieties and cultures were raised in 2- x 1-m field plots without fertilizer. A 3% foliar spray of KCl was applied 1 wk before and 1 wk after panicle initiation to half of each plot. We harvested 10 plants at random from the treated and untreated

halves of each plot. Panicle characters, grain yield, and accumulation of Na and K in the grain were estimated (see table).

Grain yield was highest in treated culture 857 (a hybrid of Vyttila 2/IR5). Vyttila 1, cultures 704 and 708, Neeraja, and CSR 13 had increased yields with treatment. The K-Na ratio was highest in Neeraja when treated, although its grain had only traces of Na when untreated. Neeraja has some mechanism to exclude Na accumulation in its tissue. Results indicate rice definitely responds to foliar K sprays and this response differs among varieties. ■

Effect of foliar spraying of K on rice grown on Pokkali soils. Vyttila, Kerala, India.

Variety	Grain (no.)		Chaff (%)		100-grain wt (g) ^b		Grain yield (g/plant)		Difference in yield (g)	Grain content					
	Treated ^a	Control	Treated	Control	Treated	Control	Treated	Control		K (%)		Na (%)		K-Na ratio	
										Treated	Control	Treated	Control	Treated	Control
Vyttila 3	65.5	93.3	19.9	12.9	3.41	2.87	9.38	18.92	(-9.54)	0.46	0.46	1.80	2.25	0.255	0.204
Culture 701	88.9	78.7	24.6	10.9	3.58	3.82	23.02	15.92	15.08	0.58	0.52	1.40	2.50	0.414	0.208
Culture 869	109.2	161.3	26.3	34.6	3.91	3.56	38.46	51.76	(-13.30)	0.50	0.56	1.40	1.15	0.357	0.486
Culture 904	90.2	87.9	15.2	14.9	3.64	3.32	28.70	43.76	(-15.06)	0.50	0.54	1.50	1.45	0.333	0.275
Vyttila 1	82.4	88.9	23.4	18.9	2.76	3.30	27.88	12.80	15.08	0.48	0.52	1.35	1.00	0.384	0.520
Culture 651	66.2	128.1	22.4	22.5	2.68	2.64	11.50	33.86	22.36	0.48	0.40	1.25	1.40	0.384	0.285
Culture 708	87.2	93.0	13.4	17.8	3.26	3.35	35.74	15.48	20.26	0.46	0.50	1.85	1.50	0.248	0.333
Culture 857	138.1	136.8	27.6	27.7	3.35	3.24	88.22	43.08	45.14	0.40	0.48	1.40	2.00	0.285	0.240
CSR13	120.1	115.7	41.5	27.1	2.78	2.12	27.16	20.32	6.84	0.44	0.52	1.40	1.50	0.314	0.346
Neeraja	115.6	131.4	20.2	18.0	2.39	2.32	38.66	36.20	2.46	0.52	0.20	1.80	Trace	0.650	0.200

^aFoliar spray of 3% M.O.P KCl. ^bMean value of 10 plants.